

An Augmented Cognition of Users to Task Performance

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Abstract

Recent research defines augmented cognition as a form of human-computer interaction where there is a tight coupling between the user and the computer achieved through physiological sensing of the user's cognitive state. This paper investigates current works in the field of augmented cognition by design and analytical tools that integrate the physiological response of the user to the straightforward visual task. The cognitive response and the baseline estimate of the physiological response can be analysed standalone in a single all-in-one process. The physiological parameters can also be accessed in real-time and help to analyse and detect stress points immediately in an instant design decision.

Keywords: Augmented cognition, Physiological response, Detected stress point, User interaction Paradigm, Real-time analysis, Cognitive state

Contribution and Purpose of Research

The contribution of this paper focuses on an augmented cognition of users to straightforward tasks, where the concepts follow the role of cognitive modeling; where there is a tight coupling between the user and the computer and this is achieved through physiological sensing of the user's cognitive state. The adopted method here first investigates current works in the field of augmented cognition by design and analytical tools that integrate the physiological response of the user to a straightforward visual task. The cognitive response and the baseline estimate of the physiological response can be analysed as a standalone in a single all-in-one process. The process helps to analyse and detect stress points immediately for a rapid design decision.

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0.1 introduction

The process of augmented cognition can be found in interdisciplinary areas such as engineering and psychology; other traditional fields such as human-computer interaction, ergonomics, and neuroscience and drawn to the cognitive aspect of the research area. Augmented cognition focuses on tasks and the environment surrounding the experimental set-up, where human system interaction already exists as a single entity. Most developers in this field leverage the tools and the findings of neuroscience to develop applications that can capture the users' cognitive state in the process of deriving a real-time computer and user system. These systems can give operational data for specifically targeted areas for the user in a task-driven context. The three areas that mostly make use of this state are the Mitigation schemes (MS), Cognitive State Assessment (CSA), and the Robust Controller, these are the subfields of science where augmented social cognition is concerned with and endeavors to enhance the ability of the users to think, reason and remember.

0.2 Literature Review

Douglas (*Engelbart [14, 12], Campbell [5], Engelbart and English [15]*) in his work released the report on augmented human intellect, which is a conceptual framework that introduces and laid down the groundwork for augmented cognition. In his paper, Engelbart (*Engelbart [13, 10], Xia and Maes [35], Campbell [6], Engelbart [8, 9, 11]*) defines the process of augmented human intellect as an increasing capability of a man to approach a complex stated problem to gain a comprehensive but suitable way to a achieve speed in solving a problem.

The main research in the way of augmented cognition began to emerge in the early 2000s, and advances in cognitive behavioural science have set the stage for the emerging field of augmented cognition (*Ashcraft [2], Arlinger et al. [1], Siemens et al. [33], Broomfield et al. [3], Hegarty [19]*). This period is mostly referred to as the 'decade of the brain', where major advancements in science and magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) (*Hu and Norris [21], Prasad [28], Jiang et al. [24], Huang et al. [22], Brown et al. [4], Lin et al. [25]*) and biometric measures have been the main pivotal research area in the emergence of augmented cognition technologies used to monitor the user's cognitive state and ability toward a straight forward task. They developed pragmatic augmented cognitive applications as the primary tools used in the controlled environment.

Also, the Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) (*GEMENTS [16], Pippine et al. [27], Groves et al. [18]*) is one of the primary funding agencies for augmented cognition, and its major focus is on the de-

velopment of more robust tools for monitoring cognitive state and integrating the process with computer systems. Their program envisions an order-of-magnitude in increasing available and net thinking resulting power from the integration of human-computer that provides clear information that is superior to basic rational individual's thinking process under the consequences of mortality. The program seeks to provide people with enhanced cognitive ability in complex situations such as stressful war conditions, it touches areas such as real-time cognitive manipulation, cognitive state detection, operational demonstration and autonomous cognitive state manipulation (*Carrera et al. [7], Si et al. [32], Ingrand and Ghallab [23], Schmorow and Kruse [30, 29], Vernon et al. [34]*). The two processes used for the proof of this concept include the real-time monitoring of the user's cognitive state and consequent management of the cognitive state of the user.

One of its drawbacks in augmented cognition is privacy concerns i.e. brain scans as a physiological measure, can arguably violate the guarantee against self-incrimination because sometimes they differ from acceptable forms of bodily evidence that can include fingerprints and blood samples, some of the evidence can be linked to the defendant mind. Another drawback is human augmentation, i.e. cases such as economic inequality may serve to exacerbate societal advantages and disadvantages due to the limited availability of basic technology, which is debated in arguments around human enhancement in augmented cognition (*Gordon [17], Hemajothi and Padave [20], Sharma and Makhija [31], Marois and Lafond [26]*). The paper tries to tackle some of these issues by utilizing a straightforward task that can help increase the thinking process in human cognition based on complex visual settings that induce cognitive ability at a higher level but in a steady and controlled environment and develop an analytic tool that interacts user response and cognitive level through phasic and tonic definition. The proceeding section discusses the methods and study.

0.3 Method

The method adopted for this project involves an experimental setup where the users sit in front of a PC with an embedded webcam that calibrates their eye movement to track user integration in the monitor, their physiological measure is monitored in real-time by placing their hand on a multimodal measuring sensor (SCR, ST and Pupil response), this records the readings to the PC. A single PC is used for low cost and time constraints and contains the cognitive analytical tool used for visualisation and analysing user activity. Forty participants were recruited, with consent to take part in the study, and each had stable and reliable conditions for the proposed experimental study for

Figure 1: Experimental setup with biosensors and user interaction with the visual interface.

Figure 2: Visual interface with predicted and initial eye movement patterns on emoji embedded icons with the emotional response of the users.

model development. Their eye movement was calibrated to the visual screen (Figure 0.1), and physiological readings from their interaction were recorded in sync with the eye movements.

0.3.1 Design of Cognitive Analytics

The tool (Figure 3) used for assessment is designed in Matlab and integrated with JAVA libraries that enable custom controls for physiological recordings and an accessible integration for multimodal system analysis. The tool enables activation of physiological parameters and detects both tonic and phasic changes by predicting eye movement and

response in synch to the other metrics; all measures depend on the baseline set for the readings.

0.3.2 The Tasks

The straightforward task is simple to interact with an already aided visual interface that has both dynamic and static contents. The visual result in the interface shows the emotional response of participants to the dynamic contents of the emoji emblem, their major task is to list the number of intersecting emoticons in a given coordinate that specifies the user’s response such as smiling, stress, and neutral emoji face. Their predicted cognitive response

Figure 3: Window interface showing finger capture used for deducting moisture content in the skin for physiological response detection to a straightforward task.

is relayed on the visual interface during analysis (Figure 0.2). The cognitive response is classified based on stressed mood while finding the task complex, neutral, relaxed, and average mood incision. The initial fixation is first recorded and the predicted response based on the cognitive stated is then indicated in a separate form from the index page of the analytical tool.

0.4 Result

Figure 0.2 shows the initial and predicted cognitive response of the user to the visual task. The initial fixation for the previous study doesn't tell much about the user response or reaction to visual contents, they simply indicate an area of fixed concentration by large fixation points and less concentration by small fixation points. The emojis help to define the reaction of the individuals from the pupil dilation and also help to understand what the person is feeling at that particular point in time. They appear as a form of bubbled sequences in tone to the physiological readings. But in this case, the resulting output in the visual display is used as stimuli. The predicted response to the cognitive state is done by a dynamic control system module embedded as an inference engine in the analytical tool (Figure 3).

We can also correlate and map out both tonic and phasic changes in the resultant response defined by the baseline of the SCR given as:

$$[R_{peaks}, R_{locs}] = \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \max(X_n) & n \geq N \quad \forall n \in X \\ \max(T_m) & m \geq N \quad \forall m \in T \end{array} \right\} \quad (0.1)$$

$$[R_{peaks}, R_{locs}] = - \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \max(X_n) & n \geq N \quad \forall n \in X \\ \max(T_m) & m \geq N \quad \forall m \in T \end{array} \right\} \quad (0.2)$$

Where R_{peaks} and R_{locs} represent the phase response at peak response in Equation 0.1 as local maxima and the tonic response in Equation 0.2 and the local minima. In a case where there is a constant latency (no response is detected), the readings are set to alter the change and set to begin again in another initial time interval.

The tonic and phasic changes can be detected from another control with a baseline for all physiological responses. The tonic phase also called the skin conductance level computes the minimum SCR data, where we assume the minimum to be set to zero and the maximum level is to be the resultant of the startle stimulus, this is the optimal tonic. This startle is a hand-clap, each SCR can be standardised

performance is based on an aggregate of the best possible response detected for each person. Complex response from the participants is predicted with a high performance of 0.99%. A similar aggregate is computed for the input parameters on the physiological response to both the Tonic and Phasic change detection. Both groups of response states are predicted with a high performance of 0.98% in both levels (local maximum and local minimum). The performance rating is based on gender group, but this does not discriminate in the perception of their cognitive response. Cognitive modeling of this form is best suited for the generalisation of its procedure.

0.5 Conclusion

This paper focuses on an augmented cognition of users to straightforward tasks, where the concepts follow the role of cognitive modeling; where there is a tight coupling between the user and the computer and this is achieved through physiological sensing of the user's cognitive state. The archetype in the interaction seeks to transform the manner and procedure in which users engage with the visual interface in the computer systems by leveraging the knowledge acquisition of cognitive state to the exact adapt user computer interaction in real-time. The adopted method here first investigates current works in the field of augmented cognition by design and analytical tools that integrate the physiological response of the user to a straightforward visual task. The cognitive response and the baseline estimate of the physiological response can be analysed as a standalone in a single all-in-one process. The physiological parameters can also be accessed in real time. The process helps to analyse and detect stress points immediately for a rapid design decision. The future directions for the research are to work more on literature review and model comparison and strive towards the application of deep learning on an advanced integrated AI system for cognitive state automatic detection in a designed experiment.

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